

COLLISION FREE SLOT ASSIGNMENT FOR WIRELESS LOW-POWER AND LOSSY NETWORKS

Mohammad Ali Sarvghadi

Tat-Chee Wan

December 5, 2018

Abstract

In Low-power and Lossy Networks (LLN) such as WSN, losing message for any reason such as collision will affect node and network life span respectively, since they are not in many cases mainly powered. This work proposes a single-hop slot assignment algorithm which can be used in TDMA. It only uses the IP address of the nodes to access medium. The proposed algorithm does not need any time synchronization and nodes synchronize their slots with neighbor nodes and save lots of energy by removing message passing exposed by time synchronization. The comparison is done with networks uses CSMA without collision avoidance. The algorithm will be tested by Cooja simulator which has based in Contiki OS. It is expected that this algorithm outperforms CSMA by minimizing collision.

1 INTRODUCTION

The promising algorithm for Low-power and Lossy Networks (LLN) such as Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) that suffer from poverty of power is Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA). Since it is collision free and guarantees the delivery of the message. It does not impose an exponential increasing delay to access medium like Career Sense Multiple Access (CSMA) [1]. TDMA does not need multiple channels with different frequencies like Frequency Division Mul-

iple Access (FDMA) [2]. Finally, it does not need high computation load like Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) [2] which does not suit LLNs. However, it has limitations, which are time synchronization and scalability [3]. Time synchronization algorithms are reviewed extensively in [4][5]. Many of them are expensive in terms of message exchange, which results in consuming energy drastically. Almost all of them do not have any mechanism or approach to avoid hidden terminal problem before nodes get synced, since most of them uses CSMA. Hidden terminal is minimized in CSMA by means of Request to Send (RTS) and Clear to Send (CTS) messages in wireless networks, but in WSNs to reduce message exchange these handshaking messages are eliminated to save more energy. Hidden terminal problem is a reason of collision, which again affects energy consumption, packet loss and throughput respectively. This work proposes an algorithm which designs and develops an enhanced MAC protocol that uses time sharing approach like TDMA and benefit LLNs. This work tends to propose a slot assignment algorithm, which minimizes the mentioned problems (extensive message passing and collision) by not synchronizing the clock of nodes, but synchronizing the time slots instead. It aims to decrease energy consumption by exchanging less messages and detecting hidden terminal by assigning slots to the nodes.

2 PROPOSED WORK

Outline of the algorithm is shown in Figure 1. It starts with a broadcast message from a specific node (normally sink node) which is called broadcaster. Afterwards, both direct neighbor of the broadcaster and broadcaster go to the waiting phase. Waiting time for direct neighbors is based on their IP address and for the broadcaster is a fix time (waiting time will be explained in 2.1). At the same time direct neighbors check the round number of the broadcaster. If the round number is 1, it means none of the slots are occupied (except the sink node that occupies slot #8) and nodes occupy the slots based on their IP address. If it is not the first round, considering that there is a probability that one or more than one slots are occupied in the first round, nodes occupy the slots based on availability. If nodes are successful, then they wait until all the slots are occupied or for a fix number of rounds. If it is not successful, round number will be increased in next superframe and nodes go to the waiting time phase again. If the broadcaster do not hear any message exchange after a fix number of rounds, it means that the slot selection process has ended. This algorithm uses 12 bytes of data payload. Using these 12 bytes, nodes can find out the progress of the algorithm as well as the situation of the slots (empty or occupied). Figure 2 shows message structure of the algorithm.

Byte #0 consists of own slot, holds the number of the slot that node occupy (these 4 bits double confirm the selection of slot marked in Byte #1). The second part is the level number of the node. **Byte #1** contains 8 time slots. Nodes mark each bit of this byte to show, which slot is occupied by them. **Byte #2** holds the round number, which increases for each round. It also holds the beacon bit that is only used by broadcaster and will be set only at the beginning of the superframe in the first round and last round to show the end of slot assignment process. **Byte #3 to #11** are signaling bytes and belong to broadcaster to verify the selected slot.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework of Method

Figure 2: Message Structure of the algorithm

2.1 Medium Access:

This algorithm is to some extent like CSMA, but it detects the hidden terminal without any handshaking messages such as RTS and CTS mentioned earlier. It uses only IP address of each node to create waiting time to access the medium. Each Superframe Time Slot (STS) in this algorithm is stretched to 8 times bigger than the normal STS, Since this work is using octet system of IP addresses. It includes 8 Fraction of STS (FSTS), which is the time to send full buffer message of including 127 bytes in 802.15.4 standard ($t_{slot} = ft_{slot} \times 8$). Before nodes occupy their own time slot and get synced, for each round, the round

number is checked and if it is odd the Least Significant Octet (LSO) of the IP address multiplied by t_{slot} plus Second LSO (SLSO) of IP address multiplied by ft_{slot} is the waiting time. If the round number is even the algorithm only exchanges the LSO and SLSO to calculate the waiting time t_{wait} . Equation 1 and 2 calculate the t_{wait} for each node. This waiting time is bounded and do not exceed the time of one superframe time (t_{frame}). Since the greatest number can be 7 for both t_{slot} and ft_{slot} ($t_{wait} \leq t_{frame}$).

$$t_{wait} = t_{slot} \times LSO + ft_{slot} \times SLSO \quad (1)$$

$$t_{wait} = t_{slot} \times SLSO + ft_{slot} \times LSO \quad (2)$$

After the waiting time is passed, nodes start to send out their messages. However, there are some special cases that may affect medium access, but before considering them, further explanation should be given regarding message structure. From 127 bytes of message in WSNs, 2 bytes belong to frame check sequence and 32 bytes belong to header. Therefore, the maximum data payload is 93 bytes. This algorithm uses maximum 12 bytes for broadcaster node and 3 bytes for direct neighbor nodes. Therefore, it only carries 37 and 46 for direct neighbor and broadcaster respectively. It means the message of this algorithm takes less time than a message with 127 bytes. If nodes are direct neighbor and can detect each others' messages in the same STS the earliest one will send the message and the rest stop sending message and stay silent until the next superframe. Therefore, there will be no collision other than they have the same octet in the least significant byte of their IP addresses (it is a rare case).

2.1.1 Special Cases

1- Two or more than two non-neighbor nodes send out their messages in the same STS (this work calls it explicit hidden terminal). For instance, the two nodes have the IP addresses of 72_8 and 12_8 . t_{wait} for them will be $2 \times \frac{7}{8}t_{slot}$ and $2 \times \frac{1}{8}t_{slot}$ respectively. Therefore, except the earliest one, the rest should be informed to change their time slots.

2- LSO and SLSO are the same for two successive rounds. They face implicit hidden terminal. In this case nodes refer to the Third LSO (TLSO) in the next superframe (replacing LSO and SLSO with SLSO and TLSO respectively) and the process will be analogous to other rounds.

2.2 Slot Assignment:

In the first round of the medium access all the time slots are empty except time slot #8 (S8 is occupied by broadcaster). Therefore, nodes start marking Byte 1 according to t_{wait} calculated based on IP address. For instance, if the IP address is 02_8 it will set bit S3 (because it has waited for $2t_{wait}$ and third slot is owed by it) in Byte 1. The two special cases mentioned earlier may occur here.

1- For explicit hidden terminal case, broadcaster node receives both messages, but assigns S3 to the earliest node, which in this case is node with IP 12_8 and mark S3 in the next superframe. However, the problem is that how do the two nodes with IP addresses of 12_8 and 72_8 (non-neighbor nodes) find out if S3 belongs to node 12_8 or 72_8 ? The question is answered by signaling bytes (bytes #4 to #11). When broadcaster starts the superframe by issuing the message in S1, it sets S3 in Byte 3 and Sf1 in Byte 5 showing that S3 belongs to the node that send message after $2.1t_{wait}$.

2- If a node stops functioning and leaves the network or a new node joins the network, it will be handled by adding one byte named Availability Byte (AByte) to the message. The added byte is marked by each node based on availability of time slots according to their direct neighbors. Therefore, if nodes do not hear from their direct neighbors for a fix time they consider it as dead and mark that time slot available in AByte. On the other hand, if a node joins the network, it starts listing to the messages exchange and check the AByte. If there is any room will occupy it.

References

- [1] O. Farrag, M. Younis, and W. D'Amico, "Mac support for wireless multimedia sensor networks," in *Global Telecommunications Conference, 2009. GLOBECOM 2009. IEEE*. IEEE, 2009, pp. 1–6.
- [2] I. Demirkol, C. Ersoy, and F. Alagoz, "Mac protocols for wireless sensor networks: a survey," *Communications Magazine, IEEE*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 115–121, 2006.
- [3] I. F. Akyildiz, T. Melodia, and K. R. Chowdhury, "A survey on wireless multimedia sensor networks," *Computer networks*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 921–960, 2007.
- [4] M. A. Sarvghadi and T.-C. Wan, "Overview of time synchronization protocols in wireless sensor networks," in *Electronic Design (ICED), 2014 2nd International Conference on*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 204–209.
- [5] —, "Message passing based time synchronization in wireless sensor networks: a survey," *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, vol. 12, no. 5, p. 1280904, 2016.